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Impact Analysis and Economic of Cluster Front Line Demonstration in Broccoli

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Abstract

The cultivation of broccoli is very popular in developed nations and in recent years, is gaining popularity in the State of Mizoram as a commercial crop because of its remunerative income, highly nutritional and medicinal properties. Krishi Vigyan Kendra Aizawl conducted the cluster front line demonstration (CFLD) during Rabi season during Rabi season of 2016-17 and 2020-21 on INM with IIHR Vegetable special in Broccoli var. CLX3512 coupled with gravity based mini sprinkler system. A total area of 45 ha was covered under the demonstration belonging to 120 farmers. The highest curd yield was obtained in CFLDs on an average (211.40 qt/ha), with 37.3 per cent more against farmers' practice (151.0 qt/ha). The extension gap was 39- 76 qt/ha, whereas the technology gap was 48-89 qt/ha. and the technology index was reduced from 31.79-17.14 % with mean value 60.4 qt/ha, 68.6 qt/ha and 24.50 % during the period under study. The demonstrated field gave higher mean gross return (Rs. 680400/ha) and mean net returns (Rs. 558875 /ha) with average benefit cost ratio of 4.6 compared to benefit cost ratio of 2.41 over farmer practices. The results highlighted the fact that yield and economics of broccoli can be enhanced by the adoption of recommended technology through Cluster Front Line Demonstrations. Hence, there is a need to disseminate the improved technologies among the farmers with effective extension methods like trainings and demonstrations.

Key word: broccoli technology gap, extension gap, horizontal, economic

Introduction:

Sprouting broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* var. *Italica* L.) is a native of Eastern Mediterranean region, derived from ancient forms of *Brassica oleracea*. Broccoli, a Latin word 'Brachium' meaning an arm or branch (Thamburaj and Singh, 2013) its sprouting is cherished for delicious taste, flavour and rich source of protein and vitamin A among cole crops. The content of vitamin A is 130 and 22 times higher than that of cauliflower and cabbage respectively. It also contains thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, vitamin C, minerals (Ca, P, K and Fe) and also rich in selenium that acts as an antioxidant. It has a very powerful anticancer compound, glycosinolates (40-80 mg/100 g fresh) which provides protection against bowel cancer. It is also a rich source of sulphoraphane, a compound associated with reducing the risk of cancer (Hazra, Chattopadhyay, Karmakar and Dutta, 2011). A 100 gm of head of broccoli head contains 89.9 g moisture, 5.5g carbohydrates, 0.2g fat, 3.3g protein, 3500 IU vitamin A, 0.05 mg thiamine, 0.12 mg riboflavin, 79 mg phosphorous, 80 mg calcium, 17 mg iron, 137 mg ascorbic acid and 37 g calories (Singh and Nath, 2012). The cultivation of broccoli is very popular in developed nations and in recent years, is gaining popularity in the State of Mizoram as a commercial crop because of its remunerative income, highly nutritional and medicinal properties. At present, broccoli is being cultivated in 163 hectares area in Aizawl District of Mizoram with production of 1,157 mt. However the average productivity of cauliflower and broccoli in the

state is 7.65 mt/ha only which is less than twice of the national average i.e. 17.34 mt/ha (Technical Bulletin No. 51 Vegetable Statistics & Horticulture Statistical, Directorate of Horticulture Govt. of Mizoram 2017). There are number of fallback reasons that includes technological know-how, non-availability of suitable variety (high yielding or hybrid), do-how, interventions, imbalanced and non judicious uses of critical inputs etc. among which most concerning factors being requirement of balance use of fertilizer and high yielding variety/ hybrid seeds. Prior to the pertaining scenarios that needed to address, scarcity of water and lack of its optimal management for effective irrigation is imminent in the region. Taking in grip to the topographic gradient that favours for opting of gravity base micro irrigation system, a judiciously selected gravity base mini sprinkler system can greatly enhance the available irrigation water management in cultivating high value vegetable crop in the region.

There is an urgent need to adopt high yielding variety and an integrated nutrient supply management system for promoting efficient and balanced use of plant nutrients. While the main emphasis was given on increasing balanced use of mineral fertilizers, the role of micronutrients, organic manure, bio-fertilizers, green manuring & recycling of organic wastes should be considered supplementary and not substitutable. On one hand, there is a vast scope for increasing plant nutrient supply through the use of organic fertilizers, but on the other hand, there is no scope for reducing the consumption of mineral fertilizers since the present level of crop productivity has to be increased in the coming years and there is no other practical low input technology available. Effective implementation of such improved agricultural practices, using a combined approach requires skilled management and addictiveness by farmers who need to be educated, demonstrated and well trained. Viewing the above scenario, the cluster frontline demonstration on INM in broccoli with IIHR Arka Special micronutrients coupled with gravity based mini sprinkler system was conducted by Krishi Vigyan Kendra Aizawl at farmers' field of Aizawl District, Mizoram, India during Rabi season of 2016-17 and 2020-21.

Materials & Methods: Krishi Vigyan Kendra Aizawl conducted the cluster front line demonstration (CFLD) during Rabi season during Rabi season of 2016-17 and 2020-21 on INM with IIHR Vegetable special in Broccoli var. CLX3512 coupled with gravity based mini sprinkler system. A total area of 45 ha was covered under the demonstration belonging to 120 farmers. High yielding hybrid broccoli var. CLX3512 was selected for cultivation which is suited and recommended for the climatic condition prevailed in the state. The nursery was raised in community participatory mode in which the leader of grower prepared nursery from seed provided at minimal price under polyhouse/ protected cultivation system (provided by KVK Aizawl under TSP programme). The ready seedlings were distributed in pattern of 1/3 utilized by them and remaining was distributed among the group members. The nursery-bed was prepared by addition of well rotten FYM or vermicompost @ 4-5 kg/ m² and maintains a width of 75-100cm. The bed was drenched with Dithane M-45 @ 2 g/l water (0.2 %) for controlling damping-off disease. Sowing was done in rows with 6-8 cm apart @ 800-850 seeds/m² and covering the bed surface with a thin layer of mixture of sand, soil and FYM/vermicompost. For control insect pest especially cabbage butter fly larvae, manual picking was done followed by spraying of Chloropyrifos or Rogor @ 3 ml/l water. Transplanting of seedlings was done after 26 days maintaining a spacing of 45x50 cm. A light irrigation was immediately provided after planting and subsequent irrigations were applied as per requirement using mini sprinkler (Turbo/ Aquamaster, Jain Irrigation). Plant population was maintained by gap filling after 6-9 days of transplanting. In order to make the field free from weeds, two manual weeding were done at 20 and 40 days after transplanting. A recommended INM dose of NPK@75:38:30 Kg/Ha + Poultry manure @ 2.5 t/ha + VC @ 2.5 t/ha along with slaked lime @ 2 t/ha & Arka Special 4 kg/ha was applied. The entire recommended dose of phosphorus, potassium and 1/3 dose of nitrogen were applied before transplanting. Fertilizers composing of urea (46% N), single super phosphate (16% P₂O₅) and murate of Potash (60% K₂O) were also applied. Before transplanting, decomposed poultry manure and vermicompost were mixed thoroughly within the top layer of the soil. The remaining dose of nitrogen was top dressed in two equal splits after 15-20 and 30-35 days of transplanting along with earthing up. In order to improve the yield and quality as well as to overcome the micronutrient deficiency of broccoli, the recommended dosage of foliar application of Arka Vegetable Special @ 75 g/15 liters of water along with 1 shampoo sachet and 2 medium sized lemons was applied at two intervals i.e. 25 & 40 days after transplanting. Weeding and other intercultural operations

were done regularly. The observations related to growth and yield parameters were recorded and analyzed. The farmer of the state solely depends on the rainwater for cultivation of crops which possesses a great challenge in the dry spell. The steep slopes and highly porous soil makes it very difficult to harvest and store water the traditional ways. In order to ensure proper irrigation of the crops in the field, harvesting of water in micro-water harvesting pond, *Jalkund* and its later use in irrigation using gravity based mini sprinkler was done under a project entitled “Micro-level water conservation and utilization technique under tough hilly terrain of Mizoram, NEH Region in India” sponsored and funded by NABARD RO, Mizoram sponsored. Harvested water at Jalkund enabled storing of water during the lean period of October to January, a total capacity of 27,000 litres. This harvested water was used for irrigation. The layout of the mini sprinkler system was designed using laterals of diameter 16mm and connected with lateral and T joins. Jain’s screen filter attached to 32mm main line was installed that were connected further to the lateral layouts using adapters, Sprinklers stakes was raised at a rise of 1-1.5 meter using locally available good quality bamboo. The calibrated discharge of the sprinkler was 50ltrs/hr. When measured, it was discharging an amount 40-45ltr/hr. Irrigation of the cultivated broccoli was scheduled in twice a week.

The technology gap is a major constraint in increasing yield and sustainability due to lack of technological know-how, non-availability of suitable variety (high yielding or hybrid), do-how, interventions, imbalanced and non-judicious uses of critical inputs etc. (Santosh kumar et.al. 2018). In keeping view of this, KVK, Aizawl, Mizoram cluster demonstration on broccoli had planned and executed with closer supervision and monitoring of the KVK Scientists with the best management practices under DFI scheme with the main aim to double farmers' income by 2022-23 is central to promote farmers welfare, reduce agrarian distress and bring parity between the income of farmers and those working in non-agricultural professions.

The gathered data on different vegetative growth parameters (leaf weight and number of leaves), yield attributing (curd weight and curd yield) and economics were processed, tabulated, classified and analyzed in terms of mean percent score and ranks in the light of objectives of the study. Using these data the differences between potential yield and demonstration plot yield (Yield gap-I), difference between demonstration plot yield and actual yield or yield under existing practice (Yield gap- II) and difference between potential yield, actual yield (Total yield gap) and impact of adoption and horizontal area spread were worked out. The extension gap, technology gap, technology index and impact of adoption and horizontal area spread were calculated using the formula as suggested by Samui et al. (2000).

Technological gap (yield gap-I) = Potential yield – Demonstration plot yield

Extension gap (yield gap II) = Demonstration – Actual yield (Farmers plot yield practice)

Total yield gap = Potential yield – Actual yield.

Technology index (%) = Technology gap/Potential yield × 100

Impact on horizontal spread area (change %) = Area after demonstration – Area before Demonstration/ Area before Demonstration × 100

Result and Discussion.

The technology demonstration results revealed that the yield and yield attributing parameters were significantly influenced in compare to farmers practices (Table 1 & 2). The results revealed that cluster FLD demonstration on broccoli recorded higher yield as compared to farmer’s practices over the years of study. The demonstrated technologies recorded average yield of 211.40 q/ha which was 37.30 percent higher than the obtained with farmer’s practices of 151.0 q/ha. In spite of increase in production yield attributed parameter also influenced significantly over the farmers practices.

Table 1: Effect of cluster front line demonstration on growth, yield attributes and yield of broccoli.

Treatment	Gross weight (g)	No. of leaves per plant	Leaf weight/pt (g)	Head weight/pt (g)	Yield (q/ha)	B:C Ratio
Technology	920.30	14.10	496.32	335.20	211.40	4.60
Local check	810.10	12.89	502.30	222.17	151.00	2.41

Extension gap, technology gap, yield index analysis

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The technology gap varied from 48 to 89 qt/ha during the study period (Table 2). The difference in technology gap in different years was due to better performance of recommended varieties with different interventions and more feasibility of recommended technologies during the course of study. The extension gap is the difference or gap between demonstration yield and farmers practices (control). Extension gap ranged from 39-76 qt/ha with the average 60.4 qt/ha during the period under study (Table 2). Santosh Kumar et.al. reported that this gap should be assigned to adoption of improved transfer technology in demonstrations practices resulted in higher head yield than traditional farmer practices. This emphasized the need to educate the farmers through various means for more adoption of improved high yielding varieties and newly improved agricultural technologies to bridge the wide extension gap. More use of new high yielding varieties by the farmers will subsequently change this alarming trend of galloping extension gap. The new technologies will eventually lead to the farmers to discontinuance of old varieties with the new technology. This finding is in corroboration with the findings of Hiremath and Nagaraju (2010). Technology Index The technology index shows the feasibility of the variety and evolved technology at the farmer's fields and a lower the value of technology index is the feasibility more. The technology index was reduced from 31.79 to 17.14 per cent during 2016-17 to 2020-21 (Table 4) which shows the higher feasibility of the demonstrated technology. This finding corroborates results of Lal et al. 2016; Meena et al. 2016 and Poonia et al. 2017.

Impact: After the adoption of recommended nutrient management practices, farmers were able to get good income in cultivation of broccoli. This technology has been horizontally expanded in the neighbouring villages and 220 farmers have adopted it covering an area of more than 163 ha. Due to its high impact and gaining popularity among the farmers community, Doordarshan National, Aizawl, Mizoram has covered the success story of a progressive farmer Mr. Darhmingliana from Sihphir village in video footage on the occasion of Field Day along with KVK staff and neighbouring farmers which was telecasted on 11.01.2021.

Table 2: Impact of CFLDs on extension, technology gap and yield index of broccoli

Year	No. of Demos	Yield qt/ha		Increase yield over the farmers practice	Extension gap	Technology gap	Technology index
		Improved practices	Farmer Practice				
2016-17	40	191	131	45.80	60	89	31.79
2017-18	40	197	158	24.68	39	83	29.64
2018-19	40	219	162	35.19	57	61	21.79
2019-20	50	232	156	48.72	76	48	17.14
2020-21	50	218	165	32.12	53	62	22.14
Mean	44	211.4	151	37.30	60.4	68.6	24.50

Economic

The performance of the technology was very promising resulting in higher yield and big size head. The yield of the demonstration plot was 211.40q/ha against 151q/ha in farmer practices. The total cost of cultivation Rs 1, 21,525/ha in demonstration plot and Rs 96,000/ha in local check plot with net profit of Rs 5, 58,875/ha and Rs 4, 41,600/ha demo and check field respectively. Adoption of INM management practices for cultivation of broccoli crop and awareness about other cultivation practices for providing technical guidance were given from time to time by KVK scientist to the farmers. Active participation of farmers were observed in implementing the recommended technologies and practices. The organization of field days at the time of harvesting was highly successful with good response by farming community, which adds significantly to their effectiveness. The experimental findings are in accordance with (Venkatreddy & Kumarprabhu, 2017 & Pawar Yogesh et al., 2018) in groundnut and (Santosh Kumar et.al. 2018) in Broccoli.

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Table 3: Effect of CFLD on economic of good horticultural practices in broccoli.

Treatment	Gross Cost (Rs)	Gross Return (Rs)	Net Return (Rs)	B:C Ratio
Technology	121525	680400	558875	4.60
Local check	96000	459200	324550	2.41

Conclusion:

The study concluded that the cluster front line demonstration organized by KVK Aizawl in broccoli is an effective tool for increasing the production and productivity of broccoli and changing the knowledge, attitude and skill of the farmers. This has not only resulted in had significantly increased yield in broccoli and rapid horizontal spread of recommended improved technologies but also helped in attaining food and nutrition security to the community. This will subsequently increase the income as well as the livelihood of the farming community. The mean per cent increment in yield of broccoli to the extent of 37.30 in demonstration over the farmers practice created greater awareness and motivated the other farmers to adopt the improved package of practices of broccoli crops. The concept of cluster frontline demonstration may be applied to all farmer categories including progressive farmers for speedy and wider dissemination of the recommended practices to other members of the farming community

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